

Navigating the Complexities of Open Science: All Sticks, No Carrots

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Introduction

Participants at the “Navigating the Complexities of Open Science” session at the 2024 FORCE11 conference at UCLA had the opportunity to consider how we overcome challenges in supporting open science, transparency, and collaboration. We began with the questions: Is open science just the latest buzzword? Does it provide an actionable framework to improve the experience of researchers and those who support them? Through an initial poll, followed by group discussions, we examined both the current pain points encountered while supporting open science and positive connotations associated with open science, working together to identify prospective solutions and actionable paths forward.

Poll results

Prior to the meeting, the session’s conveners polled the 43 registered attendees using the conference app, Whova. During the session, the poll was repeated to capture additional responses. Participants were asked to respond to the following questions:

1. Share one positive connotation or association that open science evokes for you?	2. And what's one challenge that comes to mind?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • transparency (x4) • reproducibility (x3) • collaboration (x2) • inclusivity (x2) • accessibility • better culture • better science • excelling research • fairness • gaining value from colleagues' work that can combine with mine to cover more science • international access • the potential for inclusivity and transparency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cost (x3) • convincing faculty of value/communicating value (x2) • equity (x2) • not many tangible rewards/incentives (x2) • reluctance to sharing information (x2) • silos (x2) • more work (x2) • absence of formal extrinsic incentives • changing mindsets • funding • incentive to share data • mismatch between costs and incentives • motivation • no cooperation • open does not equal free • time and costs

Group Reports

We then broke participants up into three discussion groups of 10-15 participants each to tackle three themes surfaced by the session conveners, and emphasized by the poll responses:

Theme 1: Institutional support and resources

Theme 2: Inclusivity, equity, and ethical considerations

Theme 3: Implementation and sustainability

Groups were asked to brainstorm one possible solution for a proposed (or group generated) challenge, and identify one (or more) sticking point or block to implementation.

Group 1 Notes: Putting institutional resources behind open science

The first group was asked to address the necessity for adequate financial, human, and infrastructural resources, alongside strong institutional backing, to support open science initiatives. Group 1 reported that the lack of incentives, the need to invest in people, the misplaced burden on libraries, and the difficulty of assessing open science investments are all current challenges.

This group's key takeaways included:

1. There is a **lack of incentives** to encourage participation in open science practices outside of tenure and promotion. As one participant noted, "[it's] all sticks, no carrots." Public access policies are unfunded mandates; not all federal agencies have set aside significant funds for implementing these, particularly smaller funders. "Sticks" can be effective (e.g. taking away money) means of enforcement. The group designated this

lack of incentives as a fundamental challenge and noted that researchers are not rewarded for well-documented code or data; this labor generally doesn't even appear in tenure packets. It would be useful to have a mandate from a higher level administrative research office, for example, to value, recognize, and reward open science. Until there is an incentive or mandate there will be less uptake—much of the work that goes into open science is up to individual researchers, and so an appropriate reward is important. In the interim, the group proposed recasting this lack of incentives with an appeal to personal, perhaps selfish motivations: data documentation helps one's own work and lab stay organized, increases visibility, and this better documentation makes it easier to use/reuse data.

2. Administrators need to **support and invest in people**. Open science requires investment in people or risks being added on to the workload of already busy people. The group acknowledged that these tasks often fall to the library in academic settings. In the case of preservation, specifically, there aren't other units on campus that have this as their charge. Sponsored projects offices and research computing staff have support roles but their work often stops at the end of the project and doesn't extend to making data FAIR.
 - a. As a case study example, the group discussed the adoption of transformative agreements. With funding shifting to the library (when there are no research funds the library will cover it), how will authors/researchers contribute to open science? What has been the impact of these agreements? It takes a lot of labor and staff work, beyond just monetary investment, to make these agreements work.
3. Implementing and supporting open science places a **burden on libraries**. The concept of public access sought to provide relief for libraries and funders who were well aware of the labor this required. Institutional OA policies have low compliance. Whereas funders themselves may have high compliance rates, libraries have no way of rewarding faculty who comply. Within academia, there is not clear leadership on open adoption; deans and administrators look to faculty and the disciplines themselves but all groups await a redefinition of reward structures and incentive systems. Ideally leadership must come from administration, with input and buy-in from researchers.
4. **Assessment**: Finally, the group considered how to measure investments in open science. They felt there is a lack of clarity in how to measure the success of investment in open science. For example, the University of California system collects transformative agreement data at the system-level but there is no systematic data collection for how open access is funded beyond this.

Brief summary:

Those of us who support, administer, and evaluate open science initiatives are often caught between “top down” mandates (funders, administrators) and “bottom up” efforts (local OA

compliance, assessment, data management support) which position us to make small dents in open science workflows, but not big cultural shifts. Cultivating partners outside of one's immediate role (e.g. campus partners outside of the library) can help to bridge this divide and initiate more comprehensive support for open practices, but ultimately those in leadership roles are best positioned to change the reward and incentive structure.

Group 2 Notes: Inclusive, equitable, and ethical open science

Group 2 discussed how we can ensure that open science practices are inclusive, equitable, and ethical, starting with the question: how can we encourage the recognition and visibility of all contributions during the research process?

This group's key takeaways and proposals included:

1. **Defining who counts as a participant in the research process** can prove challenging. Roles differ with wide variation across disciplines and there is no consistent approach to answering this question. To highlight this challenge, the group mentioned a National Library hosted workshop that brought together community groups, government agencies, public libraries, and people not traditionally considered researchers to discuss the idea of reciprocity. It is clear that people care both about access to data and research outputs, and also about greater participation in the research process in order to share their experiences and drive innovation. However this does not always mean they are equipped with the resources to participate in the research process or empowered to realize that they are part of that process. Exacerbating this lack of empowerment for outsider groups (such as patients) is the general inaccessibility of academic writing; plain language summaries are crucial but rarely produced.
2. Likewise, the group acknowledged a similar dilemma in **defining who counts as an expert in a field** and how trust is established and conveyed in a field. For example, they acknowledged the lack of credence given to other ways of knowing, such as indigenous knowledge organizations and systems. They also pointed to patient groups, experts in their own lived experiences, as another often neglected area of expertise. Lastly, they returned to the question of trust. Who benefits from research? Rewards structures and traditional funding sources define who has access to the resources required to participate in science and become a trusted expert in their field.
3. Considering the challenges described above, the group proposed some solutions towards creating a more equitable open research community, including **the adoption of alternate ways of considering contributions to research**, as well as **increasing the accessibility of the research itself through varied modes of sharing and communication**. The adoption of standards like persistent identifiers and the CRediT taxonomy (which formally acknowledges diverse and sometimes ignored contributions to scholarly output) have aided in highlighting that research is collaborative and produces multiple outputs. However, the general public and newer participants in open science

may not be aware of these standards. Therefore researchers must create other access points for these participants in the form of, for example, plain language summaries. A publicly available paper full of medical jargon serves little function to patients or patient advocates. While open access is a crucial starting point, researchers must also strive to make their research legible to the communities they're doing research with or about. This also includes communicating information in varied forms, such as infographics, in languages other than English, and with consideration to other time zones.

Brief summary

Open doesn't equal accessible. The roles associated with research projects vary by discipline and exist in a spectrum from participant to researcher. Whose expertise is included or excluded, whose credentials are trusted, and who is considered the "default" expert and the "default" audience for research need to be defined, and redefined to achieve equitable participation promised by open science.

As practitioners, we may feel progress is enabled through the establishment of standards, but standards and protocols that work for research managers are not necessarily enough to make research accessible and inclusive. Different modes of communication (language, timing of information sharing around the globe), and different types of output, from plain language summaries to infographics, will increase breadth of access and inclusivity of results.

Group 3 Notes: Implementation and sustainability

Group 3 dealt with the practical and systemic challenges in implementing, executing and sustaining open science efforts including commercialization and sustainability of current initiatives among other challenges.

This group's key takeaways and proposals included:

1. The group began by examining the tension between the risks of **workflow lock-in** as well as the advantages of the **commercialization** of open science platforms. **Concerns** related to commercialization centered around profit, proprietary functionality and limits to participation. The group agreed that concerns around financial instability apply to any organization regardless of their commercial or nonprofit status. The reusability of projects are then threatened when their hosting platforms are not maintained. On one hand, motivation to maintain similar software may be reduced when competing software is more readily commercialized and scaled for adoption; on the other hand, acquisition of products can negatively impact software's longevity. Regardless of the trajectory of a commercial project, proprietary functionality can limit sharing and longevity of a work. On the other hand, nonproprietary software often does not integrate with other vital services and systems and standalone solutions often underestimate the long-term resources required for maintenance and are unable to draw the large customer base needed to sustain the service. Commercial platforms may also limit participation, raising equity concerns when not every group can participate. Yet, the group acknowledged that the

resources behind a commercial product enable the scale and speed of adoption needed to achieve equitable access. Proprietary platforms can also successfully host open software and other projects, and drive the introduction of industry standards. Ultimately incentives may differ for users and vendors, but both may be driven to innovate, improve and maximize usage of commercial products.

2. The group then assessed the sustainability and long term viability of one of the highest profile solutions in open science: **academic publishing charges (APC's) for open access publishing**. On one hand, the APC model, perhaps innovative at the time of its inception, can be seen as unsustainable, either charging researchers thousands of dollars to openly publish their research or offering waivers and discounts that are not clearly communicated to those who need and qualify for them, like scientists in developing countries. On the other hand, there is evidence that read and publish agreements are highly effective in increasing the amount of research that's made open access, and that in doing so more researchers benefit from the citations and usage increases that open access publishing delivers. “
3. **Sustainability**: There will always be a cost for open access publishing and science; it remains to be seen if this long term investment will come from public or private development. Regardless, going forward, we should ask the questions: How long does something need to work to qualify as sustainable? What are the benchmarks in this process? If sustainability doesn't necessarily equate to perpetual existence, then how should it be defined? The group concluded that sustainability may be more about the existence of choice and interoperability that enables open science practices than the duration of a single platform or model's existence.

Brief summary

Sustainability is a challenge to both commercialized and open platforms and models. The lack of delineation between these entities also complicates the question as, for example, open work/code/software are sometimes embedded or hosted in commercial spaces. Some initial solutions or initiatives have ultimately proven unsustainable. For example, APC funding or waivers are difficult to scale monetarily and without additional staff support and time. The group suggested backing up and asking some foundational questions: What are the benchmarks for sustainability? Does it have to be perpetual? If not, how do we sunset programs without leaving unmet needs?

Summary

Themes that emerged:

- Full realization of open science requires and invites an ethics of care towards subjects of research, participants outside the traditional research workflows, and researchers lacking resources to engage with open research practices.
- Open science currently hinges on several unsustainable models, systems and infrastructures. We must consider long term sustainability and be flexible as we look for solutions to these unfolding problems.

Looking towards the future:

- The concept of the research community must expand to include other participants, ways of knowing, and contributors to other stages of the research process beyond scholarly output. Science itself can be deeply inequitable and we must consider who is being left behind as we embrace open science (patient groups and non-traditional research participants, non-English speakers, researchers and institutions who lack money to pay APC's, researchers in emerging regions). We must actively work to reduce existing inequities that predate the open science movement while ensuring that our engagement in open science does not exacerbate those inequities further.
- There is a positive trend in work being done to involve community members invested in but traditionally excluded from open science and research, through initiatives like the National Library workshop, standards like persistent identifiers, and more equitable authorship acknowledgments like the CRediT taxonomy.
- Although we have defaulted to the term "open science" here, terms like open research, open scholarship and open knowledge can be applied to reflect a more inclusive application of open practices in the humanities and other disciplines.
- Open science and its related practices are not a panacea, but practitioners who are willing to ask questions, challenge the status quo, experiment with new models, and iterate on past solutions will be well positioned to confront past and emerging challenges to open science and advocate for its value to the wider research community.